

both the plant and the cups. Ten adult insects were simultaneously released in each treatment. The upper end of the chimney was covered with fine nylon netting. Mortality was recorded at 12 and 24 hours after insect release.

Disulfoton and MIPC were effective fumigants in both dry and wet forms (see table). Application of their granular forms to paddy water can give good field control of BPH. ■

Ovicidal action of insecticides on brown planthopper eggs

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The brown planthopper (BPH) is an important rice pest, particularly of high yielding varieties. Because the insect thrusts its eggs into the tissues of rice leaf sheaths, insecticidal contact is difficult. Satisfactory control can be achieved only by spraying a persistent insecticide with ovicidal action.

Laboratory experiments to determine the effectiveness of various insecticides and treatments against BPH eggs laid in the leaf sheath were conducted at CRRRI (see table).

Five gravid females were caged overnight on potted plants of TN1 for oviposition. Aqueous solutions of 11 commercial insecticidal preparations were applied as foliar sprays at 0.05% concentration. Sixteen granular insecticides were broadcast at 2.0 kg a.i./ha (calculated by taking the diameter of

Effects of insecticides applied as foliar spray, paddy water broadcast application, and into the root zone on hatching of 1-, 3-, and 5-day-old brown planthopper eggs. Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, 11–20 April 1977.

Insecticide	Hatching ^a of eggs as affected by								
	Foliar spray (0.05%)			Application at 2 kg a.i./ha into					
				Standing (paddy) water			Root zone		
	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5
Carbofuran	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Carbaryl	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Quinalphos	H	H	A	H	H	H	H	H	H
Chlorpyrifos	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Monocrotophos	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Chlordimeform	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Endrin	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Phosphamidon	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Dimethoate	–	–	–	H	H	H	H	H	H
BPMC	–	–	–	A	A	A	A	A	A
MIPC	–	–	–	A	A	A	A	A	A
Ac, 92, 100	–	–	–	H	H	H	H	H	H
Fensulfthion	–	–	–	H	H	H	H	H	H
Carbaryl + lindane	–	–	–	H	H	H	H	H	H
Mephosfolan	–	–	–	H	H	H	H	H	H
Endosulfan	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Lindane	–	–	–	H	H	H	H	H	H
Chlorfenvinphos	–	–	–	H	H	H	H	H	H
Diazinon	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Phorate	–	–	–	H	H	H	H	H	H

^a A = abnormal hatching, H = normal hatching, – = not tested; max temp, 34.4°C, min temp, 22.2°C; mean max temp, 33.7°C, mean min temp, 24.3°C, mean RH, 74%.

Abnormal: Fully developed eggs with eye spots, 6 days after oviposition, pierced through the leaf sheath. At this stage, they are dying. In normal hatching, 1st-instar nymphs emerged 6 days after oviposition.

the pot) on the soil surface of the pot to simulate paddy water application. Sixteen granular insecticides were dropped directly in holes made near the rice plants to simulate root-zone placement. Each rice plant had 1-, 3-, and 5-day-old BPH eggs. The control was an untreated plant with BPH eggs. The experiment was replicated three times. The treated plants were observed

for ovicidal action (hatching or nonhatching of eggs) for 10 days.

Carbofuran applied by any method, carbaryl as foliar spray, and BPMC and MIPC applied into standing paddy water or placed in the root zone caused the ultimate death of all eggs before normal hatching. But quinalphos as a foliar spray inhibited normal hatching of 5-day-old eggs only. ■

Soil-incorporated carbofuran for control of rice whorl maggots and “early” stem borers

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Rice seedling damage caused by the rice whorl maggot *Hydrellia* sp. during the first month after transplanting has increased steadily in the Philippines in the past 10 years. Most insecticidal

sprays only partially control the pest. Granular forms of carbofuran or diazinon control the insect reasonably well where water management is good but control it poorly where rains wash the granules off the paddy. Soaking of seedling roots in solutions of granular or flowable (F) carbofuran is effective for 20 to 25 days after transplanting, but is time-consuming and messy. With F the method may be risky for those handling the solution.

IRRI field trials in the 1977 wet season with soil-incorporated granular carbofuran gave excellent control of all

insects, except brown planthopper (BPH), on the susceptible varieties IR22 and TN1 for as long as 50 days after transplanting. Control of BPH lasted 25 days.

BAEX extension specialists implemented evaluation trials with different rates of soil-incorporated granular carbofuran in farmers' fields in the 1978 wet season. They used BPI Ri-4, a new 113-day Bureau of Plant Industry rice variety (selection MRC603-303, from the cross C12// Sigadis/TN1//IR424 (Masagana 99 Group II).

BPI Ri-4 is resistant to BPH biotype 1, appears to have field resistance to biotype 2, and is moderately resistant to stem borers. Current Masagana 99 crop protection recommendations do not include insecticide control for either "early" or "late" stem borers. BPH, a minor problem in the Philippines in 1978, was serious in 1977.

The average yields from 43 irrigated rice farms in 20 provinces are shown in the table.

Soil-incorporated granular carbofuran at as little as 0.5 kg a.i./ha returned high

Average yields from 43 irrigated farmers' fields in 20 provinces, Philippines, 1978 wet season.

Insecticide rate ^a (kg a.i./ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield increase (t/ha)	Value of increase at US\$0.15/kg	Cost of US\$ granular carbofuran	Increase in profit (US\$/ha)
0	4.0	—	—	—	—
0.5	4.7	0.7	105	15	90
0.75	5.0	1.0	150	22	128
1.00	5.1	1.1	165	30	135

^a Other Masagana 99 insect control recommendations: 5 kg ZnSO₄/ha, MTMC spray at 0.75 kg a.i./ha applied to all treatments 50 days after transplanting.

profits from the control of early season insect pests, primarily the whorl maggot and stem borers, on farms.

The Philippines may recommend soil

incorporation of granular carbofuran for the Masagana 99 national rice production program for the 1979 wet season (beginning in May). ■

Evaluation of systemic effect of insecticides against brown planthopper

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Of about 100 species of insect pests that attack rice in India, the brown planthopper (BPH) is the major one in many states. BPH epidemics have become frequent since about 1970. Chemical control measures are not satisfactory because the nymphs and adults remain at the base of the rice plant and the thick plant canopy forms an air cover, preventing the insecticidal spray from reaching them. To overcome this limitation studies were conducted to identify insecticides capable of killing the insect even if they are superficially applied on the crop foliage.

Aqueous solutions of 14 commercial insecticide preparations were applied as

0.05% sprays on the upper foliage of 1-month-old potted plants of TN1. The plants' basal 15-cm portions were covered with masks. The insecticides were sprayed with a fine atomizer until the runoff stage. The sprayed plants were kept in open air for 24 hours. Then the treated foliage was cut off and the plants were enclosed in cages. Ten healthy BPH adults were confined on each plant. Mortality was recorded at 12 and 24 hours after the insects' exposure to the treated plants. The experiment was replicated three times.

Chlorpyrifos had the highest systemic effect, followed by carbofuran, quinalphos, methamidophos, dicotophos, and phosphamidon (see table). The insecticides would be promising where the dense rice canopy prevents superficial insecticidal sprays from reaching the basal plant parts, where nymphs and adults remain. ■

Evaluation of systemic effect of some candidate insecticides applied as 0.05% foliar sprays against brown planthopper adults.^a 11-13 April 1977, Central Rice Research Institute, India.

Insecticide	Corrected mortality ^b (%)	
	12 hours	24 hours
Chlorpyrifos	100	100
Phosphamidon	33	63
Carbofuran	77	77
Carbaryl	40	40
Dicotophos	50	63
Monocrotophos	33	53
Quinalphos	47	67
Dimethoate	23	43
Methamidophos	50	67
SAN 197	0	30
Vamidothion	0	0
Dichlorvos	0	0
Control	0	0

^aMax temp = 34.4°C, min temp = 22.2°C, mean max temp = 33.7°C, mean min temp = 24.3°C, mean relative humidity = 74%.

^b Treated foliage portion cut off 24 hours after insects were exposed to treatment.

Emergence of rice leaf butterfly as a rice pest in Manipur, India

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Until 1973, the rice leaf butterfly *Melanitis leda ismene* Cramer was unknown to farmers of Manipur state. The first extensive infestation of the insect in the state was in 1973 kharif in Imphal, the central district, on a few new high-yielding and two local varieties (see table). The pest was noticed in the field in early August at the maximum tillering

stage of the main second crop and infestation continued until late November when the crop was almost mature. Horned caterpillars of the butterfly fed on the

tender foliage in late morning and early evening, and sometimes caused severe defoliation. Fields planted to second crops with ensured water supply were

Infestation of rice leaf butterfly on rice. Centra district, Imphal, Manipur, India

Variety	Location	Area infested ^a (ha)	Time	Plant parts infested
IR8	Changangei	4.05	Aug	Leaves
IR24	Kakching, Yurembam, Tabungkhok	81.00	Jul-Aug	Leaves
Ratna	Kakching	16.20	Jul-Aug	Leaves
Jaya	Changangei, Thoubal	4.05	Aug	Leaves
Moirangphou (local variety)	Kakching	40.50	Aug	Leaves, stem
Phourel (local variety)	Thoubal	6.07	Aug	Leaves, stem

^aConverted from acres.